

Oximato bridged hetero-binuclear Ru^{III}-M^I complexes (M = Cu, Ag)

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Abstract : The 'complex as a ligand' strategy is employed to synthesize hetero-binuclear complexes of Ru^{III}-M^I (M = Cu, Ag). The complexes were characterized by spectral methods in particular and the cell parameters of one of the representative complex were determined to predict the structure of the complexes.

Keywords : Ru^{III}, complexes, oximato bridged, synthesis.

Introduction

Oximato bridged polynuclear complexes have been known for long¹ and there are several reports of structurally characterized²⁻¹⁰ hetero-diatomic N,O-bridged complexes of transition metal ions. In majority of the cases, the ions used are of first row transition series and examples of such complexes with heavier metal ions are few^{3,11-14}. Recently, we have explored the synthesis and characterization of the binuclear complexes of type [Ru^{III}Cl₂L₂]M^I(PPh₃)₂, **3** (M = Cu, Ag), where L is arylazooxime of type **1**.

Results and discussion

The binuclear species described herein are synthesized using mononuclear complexes containing potential donor centres to bind another metal ion. In the present work, the starting mononuclear complex is *trans*-[Ru^{III}Cl₂L(HL)], **2**¹⁵. Reactions of [Ru^{III}Cl₂L₂]⁻ (via deprotonation of **2**) with M^I(PPh₃)₂(NO₃) [M = Cu, Ag] in 1 : 1 molar ratio yielded bluish green complexes of composition [Ru^{III}Cl₂L₂]M^I(PPh₃)₂, in excellent yields.

These complexes display one Ru-Cl stretch¹⁵ in the region 350-360 cm⁻¹, indicating the *trans* disposition of the two Cl atoms and two stretches in the region 500-700 cm⁻¹ (Table 1), confirming the presence of triphenyl phosphine¹⁶. The most distinctive feature is the presence of a relatively strong band at ~1000 nm. This low energy band is attributed to ligand (π) → metal (Ru^{III}) (*t*_{2g}) charge transfer (LMCT)^{17,20} (Table 1). The complexes are paramagnetic for one electron at room temperature (Table 2)

Table 1. Spectral data for [Ru^{III}Cl₂L₂]M^I(PPh₃)₂

Complex	UV-Vis data λ _{max} , nm (ε, M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)	IR data (cm ⁻¹)	
		ν _{Ru-Cl}	ν _{PPh₃}
[Ru ^{III} Cl ₂ L ¹ ₂]Cu ^I (PPh ₃) ₂	1020 (2400), 605 (3010), 450 (4530), 400 (5540)	350	510, 710
[Ru ^{III} Cl ₂ L ² ₂]Cu ^I (PPh ₃) ₂	1010 (2600), 610 (3220), 440 (4710), 400 (5870)	360	510, 700
[Ru ^{III} Cl ₂ L ¹ ₂]Ag ^I (PPh ₃) ₂	1020 (2350), 580 (2710), 450 (4860), 410 (6020)	365	500, 700
[Ru ^{III} Cl ₂ L ² ₂]Ag ^I (PPh ₃) ₂	1005 (2230), 590 (2930), 460 (5110), 410 (6160)	365	510, 700

as expected for ruthenium(III) (Cu^I , Ag^I are d^{10} systems, having no contribution). Usually in such species, the spin-lattice relaxation is rapid and hence low temperature EPR spectra needs to be recorded¹⁷. It has been found that the complexes $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}_2]\text{M}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2$, display characteristic resonance signals at room temperature in polycrystalline state and the spectra is essentially the same in frozen condition (Table 2, Fig. 1).

Complex	μ_{eff} (BM)	EPR data		
		g_1	g_2	g_3
$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}^1_2]\text{Cu}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2^a$	1.90	2.357	2.357	1.988
$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}^2_2]\text{Cu}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2^b$	1.95	2.329	2.329	1.944
$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}^1_2]\text{Ag}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2^b$	1.98	2.318	2.247	2.024
$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}^2_2]\text{Ag}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2^a$	2.04	2.369	2.278	2.034

^aEPR in polycrystalline sample at 298 K.
^bEPR in frozen dichloromethane-toluene at 77 K.

Fig. 1. EPR spectra of $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}^2_2]\text{Cu}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ in frozen dichloromethane-toluene at 77 K.

The X-ray structure of $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}^1_2]\text{Cu}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ has not been determined but its cell parameters (Table 3) are analogous to those of $[\text{Rh}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}_2]\text{Cu}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2^3$, suggesting that they are isomorphous. Thus the geometry of $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}_2]\text{M}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ complexes can be represented by **3** and the net reaction for its synthesis can be shown by Scheme 1.

Experimental

General consideration :

The starting complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{NO}_3)^{18}$,

Scheme 1. Synthesis and geometry of $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}_2]\text{M}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ complexes ($\text{M} = \text{Cu}, \text{Ag}$).

$\text{Ag}(\text{PPh}_3)_2(\text{NO}_3)^{19}$ and $\text{trans}-[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}(\text{HL})]^{15}$ were synthesized as reported. All chemicals and solvents are of reagent grade and were used as received. Electronic and IR spectra were recorded respectively with a Shimadzu UV-1601 PC and Nicolet Magna IR Series II/Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrometers. Room temperature magnetic susceptibility was measured with a Model 155 PAR vibrating sample magnetometer fitted with a Walker Scientific L75FBAL magnet. Microanalysis (C, H, N) were performed using Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. EPR spectra were recorded in the X-band on a Varian E-109 spectrometer fitted with a quartz Dewar. For measurement at 77 K, the Dewar was filled with liquid nitrogen and DPPH ($g = 2.0037$) was used to calibrate the spectra.

Crystals of $[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}^1_2]\text{Cu}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ ($0.38 \times 0.30 \times 0.32 \text{ mm}^3$) were grown by slow diffusion of hexane into the dichloromethane solution of the complex. The cell parameters of the complex were determined by least-squares fit of 30 machine centred reflections ($2\theta = 15-30^\circ$) on a Siemens R3m/V four circle diffractometer with graphite monochromated $\text{MoK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) and are listed in Table 3.

Synthesis of the complexes :

$[\text{Ru}^{\text{III}}\text{Cl}_2\text{L}^1_2]\text{Cu}^I(\text{PPh}_3)_2$: 0.2 g (0.32 mmol) of *trans*-

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{62}\text{H}_{56}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{P}_2\text{CuRu}$
Crystal size (mm^3)	$0.38 \times 0.30 \times 0.32$
a (\AA)	13.168 (7)
b (\AA)	13.582 (6)
c (\AA)	19.520 (9)
α ($^\circ$)	74.19 (3)
β ($^\circ$)	81.56 (4)
γ ($^\circ$)	67.92 (4)
Crystal system	Triclinic

[RuCl₂(HL¹)L¹] was suspended in 15 ml of ethanol and to it 0.013 g (0.33 mmol) of sodium hydroxide was added. The contents were stirred till dissolution and the brownish solution so obtained was filtered. To the filtrate an ethanolic solution of Cu(PPh₃)₂(NO₃) (0.198 g, 0.32 mmol) was added and stirred, when the solution turns intense blue green. The contents were allowed to stir for 3 h when dark coloured precipitate separated out. It was then filtered, washed with 1 : 1 ethanol and dried in vacuum over fused CaCl₂ (yield : 0.318 g, 81.3%) (Found : C, 60.85; H, 4.35; N, 6.77. Calcd. for C₆₂H₅₆N₆O₂Cl₂P₂CuRu : C, 61.31; H, 4.65; N, 6.92%).

[Ru^{III}Cl₂L²]₂Cu^I(PPh₃)₂ : Yield : 68%. Found : C, 61.17; H, 4.64; N, 6.57. Calcd. for C₆₄H₆₀N₆O₂Cl₂P₂CuRu : C, 61.86; H, 4.87; N, 6.76%.

[Ru^{III}Cl₂L¹]₂Ag^I(PPh₃)₂ : 0.2 g (0.32 mmol) of *trans*-[RuCl₂(HL¹)L¹] was suspended in 15 ml of ethanol and to it 0.013 g (0.33 mmol) of sodium hydroxide was added. The contents were stirred till dissolution and the brownish solution so obtained was filtered. To the filtrate an ethanolic solution of Ag(PPh₃)₂(NO₃) (0.212 g, 0.32 mmol) was added and stirred, when the solution turns intense blue green. The contents were allowed to stir for 4 h when dark coloured precipitate separated out. It was then filtered, washed with 1 : 1 ethanol and dried in vacuum over fused CaCl₂ (yield : 0.323 g, 84.3%) (Found : C, 58.77; H, 4.33; N, 6.54. Calcd. for C₆₂H₅₆N₆O₂Cl₂P₂CAgRu : C, 59.15; H, 4.48; N, 6.68%).

[Ru^{III}Cl₂L²]₂Ag^I(PPh₃)₂ : Yield : 68%. Found : C, 58.37; H, 4.48; N, 6.31. Calcd. for C₆₄H₆₀N₆O₂Cl₂P₂CAgRu : C, 58.98; H, 4.64; N, 6.45%.

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